

Evaluation of Website Content of Selected Central Universities Libraries of India: An Analytical Study

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *The study evaluates the content quality and functional features of library websites of selected Central Universities in India, with the aim of assessing their digital visibility, usability, and readiness to support academic engagement. It seeks to compare institutional performance and identify strengths and gaps influencing website effectiveness and ranking outcomes.*

Methodology: *A descriptive and analytical approach was adopted using content analysis. Five Central University library websites were selected based on their National Institutional Ranking Framework positions. Data was collected through direct online observation using a structured checklist comprising 50 indicators grouped under general information, website features, library resources, library services, web-based interactive tools, and browser compatibility. Each indicator was scored dichotomously, and aggregate scores were used to rank the websites.*

Findings: *The results reveal notable variation in website content and functionality among the institutions. Aligarh Muslim University ranked highest with comprehensive coverage across most indicators, followed by the University of Delhi and Jawaharlal Nehru University. While general information and browser compatibility were well represented across all libraries, significant deficiencies were observed in interactive and engagement-oriented features, particularly the limited adoption of web-based participatory tools. Differences in service presentation and resource visibility also affected overall rankings.*

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***Implications:** The study highlights the need for systematic content standardization, regular updates, and greater integration of interactive features to enhance user engagement. Strengthening library websites can improve institutional visibility, support academic communication, and contribute to improved digital standing in national and global academic environments.*

Keywords: Central Universities, Content Analysis, Website visibility, Library Website, Academic Library

1. INTRODUCTION

Academic library websites function as portals that relay details pertaining to the different amenities, services, and resources the library offers. As digital access points, they provide students and faculty with online access to library catalogs, electronic resources, and instructional materials and various digital content (Parmar et al., 2022 and Yumnam et al, 2021). Users can view and procure academic materials, order interlibrary loans, and query scholarly databases or research articles online and remotely. These websites are also integrated with different services and tools to provide users with the most relevant and current content. As integrated tools and services advance, academic library websites continue to provide the most relevant support for teaching, learning, and research to the various users (Aharony, 2012).

Currently, individuals are able to obtain information rapidly and effortlessly through the use of search engine tools. It serves as a representative for an organization. The website of an educational institution serves as a resource for discovering academic news, courses, student life, and other valuable information for students or those interested in learning about the institution. This paper examines the information on educational universities websites to identify the relationship between the website's rankings. The findings of this paper will assist universities website administrators in generating content for their sites while taking into account the duration users spend on the site. Additionally, the outcome from the tool will prompt them to elevate their website in the Web Ranking of World Universities (Madu et al., 2024). In the era of ICT, academic libraries encounter challenges in fulfilling patrons' information requirements, spanning from basic publications to digital resources. A few decades ago, users had simple library needs, which library staff could resolve by eliminating certain print materials or recommending users to sister libraries. Currently, library services users do not need to report to libraries in person; they can access library services from any part of the globe by visiting library sites. For the rendering of services that are effective and timely, digital libraries offer diverse materials, and the digital library sites provide necessary tools for users. The library services of the World Wide Web and Digital Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) tools provide libraries and users with a new ineffable paradigm. Information libraries face the challenge of information obsolescence (Dwivedi and Pachauri, 2023). Libraries are forced to devise new and innovative ways to provide services to their users. The combination of Online Digital Libraries and library internet services has improved library services in all environments, and especially in academic environments. In these environments, library websites are the most important knowledge information sources and provide access to up-to-date, accurate information in the formats most suited to users.

1.1. Central Universities

Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU), Jamia Millia Islamia (JMI), University of Delhi (DU), Banaras Hindu University (BHU), and Aligarh Muslim University (AMU) constitute some of the central and most prominent educational institutions of the country and have recognition of national importance and distinctive academic legacies. JNU, based in New Delhi, is notable for its research, social sciences, and liberal thought (Kaur et al., 2020). JMI is also in the capital; recently, the historical and cultural identity of JMI built during the freedom movement, has transformed into a contemporary university with various advanced programs. DU is one of the most prominent and the oldest educational institutions in India, has a diverse academic and vibrant student community. BHU is in the city of Varanasi and has one of the largest residential university campuses of Asia; BHU integrates modern disciplines with traditional Indian values. Aligarh Muslim University in Aligarh has a glorious past. These institutions have and continue to cater to millions of students in the country and abroad. These institutions also have a major impact in the area of research, public policy and broader national discourse. Each of these institutions has a central library of considerable scope in all levels of educational and digital resources (Sharma, 2018).

To meet adequately modern demands, including e-resources, online catalogues, and user-centric websites, their libraries strive to evolve continuously. However, inequalities still exist regarding the content and services of these websites. AMU is at the forefront pertaining to the functionality of these sites, while the others, especially JNU and DU, also provide considerable academic support. Most of these sites still show considerable room for digital growth due to the limited incorporation of Web 2.0 technologies. Overall, these central universities continue to play a crucial role in the evolution of higher education in India.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Sandeep S. Pradhan (2025) In this research paper is to examine the information content available on the library websites of universities in Maharashtra. Research aids in evaluating the precision and user-friendliness of library websites through the application of various content analysis dimensions. **N. L. N. P Junurham et al. (2025)** This research suggests standardizing website creation, improving accessibility, and adopting user-focused policies to enhance digital platforms and elevate remote library services

Meenal Oak and Dhiraj Chogale (2025) The research is a thorough content analysis aimed at assessing the accessibility and informational depth of library websites at chosen higher education institutions, concentrating on architecture and planning fields. The assessment encompasses factors like navigation tools, accessible resources, digital offerings, and user interaction components.

Madhu S and Kannappanavar B.U. (2024) The study analyzes the websites of 28 NIRF-ranked South Indian pharmacy institutes' libraries, revealing that 7.14% use open-source CMS. Most libraries (96.43%) provide basic information, while 85.71% include details on e-journals and e-books. Half offer services like ILL, remote access, and reprographics and 42.86% mention e-learning platforms. The study shows that many libraries lack Web 2.0 technologies, with only half meeting predefined content criteria, suggesting a need for user-friendly website improvements.

Kinjal G. Parmar et al. (2022) This study examines the web content and design trends of agricultural university library websites in Gujarat, focusing on basic information, resources, e-learning platforms, and Web 2.0 services. A checklist was used to evaluate the sites based on literature. It highlights the importance of regularly updating and maintaining library websites to meet user demand. The findings reflect the growing role of IT in transforming library content for the digital era.

Gyanajeet Yumnam and Ch. Ibohal Singh (2021) A comprehensive checklist has been formulated to gather data regarding library amenities, library holdings, accessibility of university web pages, link searches, and the retrieval interface. The objective of this paper is to assist website administrators in acquiring a more profound comprehension of the existing condition of these university websites, thereby enabling them to offer more informative, contemporary, reliable information, as well as user-centric and dynamic methodologies tailored to the needs of users.

R. Sharma (2018) measured the usability, navigation and frequency of updates of central university library websites. The research discovered that the majority of the websites offered user-oriented services, which were however not consistent in the information structure. The authors recommended that library websites be redesigned in a standard web design.

3. OBJECTIVES

- To verify fundamental library details on the library websites.
- To evaluate the online material of five chosen Central Universities Library websites.
- To understand the existing services and resources available on the five chosen Central Universities Library websites.
- To categorize the websites of the library of five chosen Central Universities based on this research.

4. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This research included selected top Central Universities from India. These establishments indicated in table 1 according to the ranking under the National Institutional Ranking Framework 2025, released on the portal of the MoE, Government of India.

Table-1: Five Central Universities on NIRF (2025)

Sl. No.	University	Ranking
1.	“Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU)”	2
2.	“Jamia Millia Islamia (JMI)”	4
3.	“University of Delhi (DU)”	5
4.	“Banaras Hindu University (BHU)”	6
5.	“Aligarh Muslim University (AMU)”	10

5. METHODOLOGY

This research is developed with carefully planned and effectively structured 50 checklists derived from earlier relevant documents for data gathering. In the research, five central universities of India have been selected on the basis of their top five NIRF ranking (universities category). Information gathered from the online exploration of library websites from five chosen Central Universities in India. Data examined and displayed in tabular format using MS-Excel. Every checklist is verified with a "✓" or "✗" mark. Each "✓" gets a point (1), while each "✗" gets a point (0).

6. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The current research examined the 50 checklists across different categories, including general information, features of library websites, and details about library services, library resources, web 2.0 capabilities, and compatibility with web browsers.

6.1. General Information

Table 2 presents general details about the library websites of chosen AMU achieved 10 (100%) points, while DU secured 9(90%), JNU secured 08 (80%) and JMI and BHU obtained 7(70%). AMU showcased all the aspects listed under general information on their library websites.

Table-2 Website General Information

Features	JNU	JMI	DU	BHU	AMU
About the library	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mission	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓
Objective	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓
Membership	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓
Library Rules	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓
Contact Us	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Collection	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Library Staff	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓
Library Policy/SOP	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓
Library Timings	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
Total = 10 (100%)	08 (80%)	07 (70%)	09 (90%)	07 (70%)	10 (100%)

6.2. Website Feature

Table 3 illustrates the features of central library websites from chosen central universities showcased functionalities on their library website. BHU achieved the highest score of 08 (80%), with DU and AMU next at 06 (60%) and third ranks hold by JNU and JMI 05 (50%) each.

Table-3 Library Website Feature

Features	JNU	JMI	DU	BHU	AMU
Library Separate Homepage	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Website Updating Date	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗
Login/Registration	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓
Media/ Photo Gallery	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Feedback	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓
Keywords Search	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗
Form Download	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
Title of the Library at the Page's Top	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Multilingual	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓
Links to Other Institution	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗
Total = 10 (100%)	05 (50%)	05 (50%)	06 (60%)	08 (80%)	06 (60%)

6.3. Library Resources Information

Table 4 presents details regarding the library resources from the websites of chosen JMI received 09 (90%) points, while JNU, BHU and AMU scored 08(80%). DU listed with 06(60%) attributes beneath the section regarding library resource information.

Table-4 Library Resources

Features	JNU	JMI	DU	BHU	AMU
Print Book	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Print Journals	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
E- Books	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
E-Journals	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Online Databases	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Video Resources	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓
Open Access Resources	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗
Writing Supporting Tools	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓
Institutional Repository	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
CD/DVD Resources	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗
Total = 10 (100%)	08(80%)	09(90%)	06(60%)	08(80%)	08(80%)

6.4. Library Services

Table 5 displays the library services of chosen Central University central library's websites. JNU achieved the highest score of 07 (70%), while JMI, DU and AMU followed with 6 (60%), BHU had the lowest with 4 (40%).

Table-5 Library Services

Features	JNU	JMI	DU	BHU	AMU
Newspaper Clipping	X	X	X	X	✓
Ask Librarian	✓	X	X	X	X
New Arrivals	X	✓	✓	✓	X
Inter Library Loan	✓	✓	✓	X	✓
Web OPAC	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
FAQ's	✓	X	X	X	X
Reprography Information	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Library Orientation/Guide	✓	✓	✓	X	✓
Research Support	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Question Paper	X	X	X	X	X
Total = 10 (100%)	07(70%)	06(60%)	06(60%)	04(40%)	06(60%)

6.5. Web 2.0 Features

Table 6 shows the web 2.0 characteristics for the chosen Central University central library's websites. DU and AMU only received 3(75%), while JNU, JMI and BHU obtained 00 (0%) points.

Table-6 Web 2.0 Feature

Features	JNU	JMI	DU	BHU	AMU
Blog	X	X	X	X	X
Facebook	X	X	✓	X	✓
Twitter	X	X	✓	X	✓
YouTube	X	X	✓	X	✓
Total = 04 (100%)	00(0%)	00(0%)	03(75%)	00(0%)	03(75%)

6.6. Compatibility with Web Browsers

Table 7 showcases the compatibility features of web browsers on the central library websites of chosen central universities. All chosen IISERs received maximum points 6(100%) for web browser compatibility.

Table-7 Compatibility with Web Browsers

Features	JNU	JMI	DU	BHU	AMU
Google Chrome	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mozilla Firefox	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Opera	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Internet Explorer	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Ulaa	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Opera	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Total = 06 (100%)	06(100%)	06(100%)	06(100%)	06(100%)	06(100%)

6.7. Library Websites Ranking of Chosen Central Universities

Table 8 displays the ranking of central library websites for chosen central universities. The ranking was created according to points assigned to specific library websites of central universities based on the web content present on their respective sites. AMU secured the top position with 39 points out of 50, while DU placed second with 36 points. JNU secured the third rank with 34 points out of a total of 50, while JMI and BHU took the fourth spot with 33 points out of 50.

Table-8: Library Websites Ranking

Features	JNU	JMI	DU	BHU	AMU
General Information (n=10)	08	07	09	07	10
Information on Library Resources (n=10)	05	05	06	08	06
Information on Library Resources (n=10)	08	09	06	08	08
Library Services (n=10)	07	06	06	04	06
Web 2.0 Features (n=4)	00	00	03	00	03
Web Browser Compatibility (n=6)	06	06	06	06	06
Total = 50	34	33	36	33	39
Rank	3	4	2	4	1

7. FINDINGS

7.1. AMU Leads Overall in Library Website Quality

Aligarh Muslim University (AMU) has the most comprehensive and organized library website among selected central universities and ranks first with a score of 39/50. It garnered complete marks in General Information and Web Browser Compatibility and excelled in most other areas.

7.2. DU and JNU Follow in Overall Ranking

DU and JNU secured 2nd and 3rd positions respectively, with DU scoring 36/50 and JNU 34/50. DU particularly excelled in Web 2.0 Features and General Information, while JNU performed best in Library Services.

7.3. JMI and BHU Share Fourth Rank

JMI and BHU both scored 33/50, sharing the 4th position. Despite their lower overall scores, JMI performed well in Library Resources Information, while BHU topped the list in Library Website Features.

7.4. General Information Well-Represented Across All Universities

Most universities performed strongly in this section, with AMU achieving 100% and DU 90%. The consistent inclusion of basic elements like “About the Library”, “Library Timings”, and “Contact Details” highlights the importance given to transparency and accessibility.

7.5. Lack of Integration of Web 2.0 Features

Most library websites did not incorporate Web 2.0 applications (social media, blogs, YouTube, etc.). Only AMU and DU included these tools and received scores of 3/4 each, while JNU, JMI, and BHU received 0, demonstrating a lack of user engagement and outreach.

7.6. Uniform Web Browser Compatibility

All five central universities scored 100% in web browser compatibility, confirming that their websites are accessible through all major browsers, ensuring a consistent user experience.

7.7. Need for Consistent Updates and Interactive Features

Most structural and informational facets of a website are in place, but elements like Login/Registration, FAQs, Multilingual support, and feedback loops are inconsistently available. Improved website updating and the addition of interactive components would better serve users.

8. CONCLUSION

To sum up, this paper demonstrates that the library web site of Aligarh Muslim University (AMU) is rated the most quality web site throughout the curriculum. The AMU projects in terms of the information they provided and technical skills were discovered to be more informative. DU and JNU universities were ranked second and third respectively with DU and JNU doing well in Web 2.0 features and library services respectively. Jamia Millia Islamia (JMI) and Banaras Hindu University (BHU) were at the fourth place. All project curriculums showed information generality and access to web browsers. Nevertheless, the majority of the projects were not equipped with Web 2.0 tools and connectivity capabilities, which restrained the linkage and interaction of the users. The analysis indicates that such aspects as frequent updates and inclusivity can be included in the library projects to make them more efficient. To enhance their global reputation, Indian universities need to prioritize research quality, digital resources, and strategic outreach, guaranteeing that academic excellence goes hand in hand with robust online presence and international partnerships.

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